

Supplementary Material

S1. Computable General Equilibrium Model

The d-PLACE model is a recursive-dynamic global computable general equilibrium (CGE) model developed at the Centre for Climate and Energy Analyses, part of the National Centre for Emissions Management, under the Institute of Environmental Protection – National Research Institute (IOŚ-PIB). The model simulates economic activity over time while accounting for interactions between sectors, regions, and environmental policies. The production process in the model is represented using nested constant elasticity of substitution (CES) production functions, which allow for substitution between inputs such as labour, capital, and energy. The model distinguishes 20 sectors/commodities, including energy-intensive industries like electricity and heat generation, refined oil, chemicals, non-metallic minerals (e.g., cement-lime-gypsum, glass), paper and pulp, iron and steel, non-ferrous metals (including aluminium), and mining (see table S1). For a detailed description of the model structure, see the documentation provided by IOŚ-PIB (2022).

SECTOR SHORT NAME	SECTOR NAME
FORESTRY	Forestry
OIL	Refined oil products, coke, nuclear fuels
GAS	Natural gas (extraction and service activities)
PAPER	Paper–pulp–print
CEMENT	Non-metallic minerals
ELECTRICITY	Electricity
GDT	Gas distribution and heating
COAL	Coal (mining and agglomeration)
CRUDE	Crude oil (extraction and service activities)
MANUFACTURING	Other manufactures
IRON & STEEL	Iron and steel industry
CHEMICAL	Chemical industry
FOOD	Food industry
SERVICES	Services
AGRICULTURE	Agriculture and fishing
TRANSPORT	Other transport
AVIATION	Air transport
NON-FERROUS MET.	Non-ferrous metals
CONSTRUCTION	Construction

VEHICLES

Motor vehicles and parts and transport
equipment nec

Table S1. List of sectors included in the dPLACE model.

Geographically, the model includes 19 regions spanning the globe: Australia, Benelux, Brazil, Central Europe, China, Germany, EFTA countries, France, Iberia and Italy, India, Japan, Northern Europe, OPEC, Poland, Russia, South-East Europe, the UK and Ireland, the USA, and the rest of the world. A detailed discussion of the regional structure is also included in IOŚ-PIB (2022).

The d-PLACE model operates in a recursive-dynamic manner, solving in 5-year steps from the base year 2014 to 2050, except for the first step, which spans one year (2014–2015). The solution for the base year represents the state of the global economy in 2014. To calibrate the model, share parameters in the production functions are adjusted to match observed economic data for that year, from the GTAP-10 (Global Trade Analysis Project) database.

The solution for the subsequent periods is obtained after updating several technological and policy parameters. First, we assume that the productivity of labour grows at the growth rate equal to GDP growth projections from the EU Reference Scenario 2020 (De Vita et al. 2021). In Poland, the average annual growth rate is 2.9% in the 2020s and 1.8% in the 2030s. Second, we compute the level of capital in each period using the standard capital accumulation rule: the level of capital depends on prior-period investment and depreciation. The initial level of capital is estimated using Solow's (1957) steady-state formula: initial investment is divided by the sum of the depreciation rate (assumed to be 7% annually) and initial GDP growth rate. Investment in each period is determined by the ratio of the capital rental rate to the price of investment goods, consistent with the Australian tradition of CGE modelling (Dixon and Rimmer, 2002). Third, technological progress is incorporated into the model using projections for emissions, fuel intensities, energy system costs, and energy sector investments, based on Rabięga et al. (2021) and Tatarewicz et al. (2021). These studies assume emission reduction targets consistent with those used in this model. Over time, we impose tighter emissions targets, with further details on these targets and their implementation described in Supplementary material S2.

The dynamic evolution of technology and policy parameters affects labour demand across sectors, leading to a reallocation of labour. In the Polish economy, the largest adjustment is expected in the coal mining sector, where declining coal consumption reduces labour demand. The speed of this transition depends in turn on factors such as (i) the price of emissions allowances under the EU Emissions Trading System (EU-ETS), (ii) energy efficiency improvements, (iii) substitution between energy carriers, and (iv) the change in imports caused by outsourcing emissions-intensive production (leading to carbon leakage).

The price of emissions in EU-ETS is determined by equilibrium on the market for emission allowances: total emissions from the sectors covered by the EU-ETS system must equal the fixed supply of allowances each year. Countries and regions can freely trade allowances, leading to a uniform allowance price across the EU. This trade flexibility means that emission reductions may differ between regions. For example, a region with lower abatement costs (e.g., due to higher renewable energy potential) may reduce emissions more quickly in the early years than others.

Energy efficiency improvements in the model have two components. The first is autonomous energy efficiency improvements (AEEI), representing exogenous technological advancements independent of price changes. This can be interpreted as an improvement driven by global technological changes, such as innovations in heat pumps or new materials allowing for better thermo-isolation of buildings. We assume that the AEEI decreases energy intensity annually by 1% for production sectors and 2% for households. The second component is price-driven efficiency improvements, where higher energy prices encourage firms to reduce energy use relative to capital. For instance, rising fuel costs may lead firms to retrofit buildings or adopt energy-efficient equipment. These price-driven improvements are determined endogenously within the model as firms optimize their energy–capital ratios. We assume that elasticity of substitution between capital and energy is equal to 0.75 in services and 1 in all other sectors. In the sensitivity analysis we also run the simulations when the elasticity takes the values of 0.5 and 1.5.

The substitution between energy carriers takes place due to firms' optimisation of costs within each sector as well as through a change in the sectoral composition of the economy. Within each sector, we assume that firms combine energy inputs - coal, gas, oil, electricity, and heat - using constant elasticity of substitution (CES) technology.

We assume that elasticity of substitution is equal to 2.5. In the sensitivity analysis we also run the simulations when the elasticity takes the values of 2.0 and 3.0. In addition, we assume that natural gas can be substituted with hydrogen (the two fuels are perfect substitutes). The change in sectoral composition is a consequence of a change in the prices of inputs: more emission-intensive sectors suffer larger increases in the cost of production and therefore larger drops in demand.

S2. Emission targets.

The targets for the EU countries are computed in three steps. First, we specify the total reduction of GHG emissions for the entire EU economy, which is consistent with the amended EU climate policy (European Commission, 2020a): a net reduction target for 2030 of 55% as compared to 1990 emissions and continued efforts to achieve net zero GHG emissions by 2050 (i.e. considering removals from the LULUCF sector). This level of GHG emission reductions contributes to the EU's goal, as outlined under the Paris Agreement, to limit global temperature change by 1.5°C (European Commission, 2018). Without including removals, the assumed implementation of the EU's climate policy targets for GHG emission reductions is estimated to be 53% in 2030 and 76% in 2040, relative to 1990. This target is less ambitious than the European Commission's recent proposal to cut emissions by 90% by 2040. (European Commission 2024).

year	Total GHG emissions reduction compared to 1990	Emission reduction target in EU ETS compared to 2005	Emission reduction target in non-ETS compared to 2005
2030	53%	60%	40%
2040	76%	83%	67%

Table S2: Total GHG emissions reduction with separate targets for EU ETS and non-ETS for EU-28 in the decarbonization scenario

Second, we divide the emissions between the emission covered by the EU ETS and remaining sectors (non-ETS). In the climate policy scenario, the distribution of reduction targets between the EU ETS and non-ETS sectors for 2030 and for 2040 was largely based on the impact assessment presented in September 2020 for the EC communication:

‘Stepping up Europe’s 2030 climate ambition’ (European Commission, 2020c) and emission reduction path in the European Commission Global Energy and Climate Outlook (EC GECO2020) projection for the 1.5°C scenario (European Commission, 2020b). We calculated that emissions in the EU ETS are to be reduced by 60% in 2030 and 83% in 2040. In this case, the non-ETS sectors would need to cut emissions by 40% in 2030 and 67% in 2050 relative to 2005 (see table S2).

Finally, in non-ETS sectors, according to the Effort Sharing Regulation (European Parliament, 2018), the overall EU’s emission reduction is converted into national emission reduction targets in 2030 and 2040. The assumed redistribution of the reduction effort in non-ETS was based on the GDP per capita following the Effort Sharing Regulation. Less wealthy states were assigned less ambitious targets due to potentially higher economic growth in the future and their lower investment capacity today. The national targets for the EU member states are ranging from 10% to 50% for the year 2030 and from 35% to 75% for the year 2040 compared to 2005 emissions. For Poland, the reduction target in the non-ETS is assumed to be 18% and 46% compared to 2005 emissions for the years 2030 and 2040, respectively.

We assume that regions outside the EU considered in the modelling scenario will adopt binding emission limits/reduction targets included in the NDCs submitted under the Paris Agreement. GHG reduction targets for regions outside the EU were estimated based on the GHG emission projection in 2030 and 2040 from the EC GECO2020 (European Commission, 2020b) projection for the ‘New Normal’ scenario. For these regions, each target is binding at the region level.

S3. Structural change due to climate policy

This supplementary material contains projections on structural change, fuel demand as well as detailed results on output and employment by sector in Poland in the simulation with labour market frictions. The primary purpose of this section is to shed light on the drivers of shifts in demand for sectors, especially the mining sector.

Figure S1: GDP, energy supply and electricity dynamics in the decarbonization simulation with labour market frictions in Poland

Figure S2: Dynamics of fuel consumption in the decarbonization simulation with labour market frictions in Poland

Figure S3: Dynamics of output and employment in the mining sector in Poland in the decarbonization simulation with labour market frictions

Figure S4. Dynamics of output by sector in the simulation with frictions.

Figure S4 continued. Dynamics of output by sector in the simulation with frictions.

Figure S4 continued. Dynamics of output by sector in the simulation with frictions.

Figure S5. Dynamics of employment by sector in the simulation with frictions.

Figure S5 continued. Dynamics of employment by sector in the simulation with frictions.

Figure S5 continued. Dynamics of employment by sector in the simulation with frictions.

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